

DEFINITE-CCRI

Shortlist of projects receiving PDA support

(Deliverable 2.5)

Deliverable Number	D 2.5
Deliverable Name	Shortlist of projects receiving PDA support
Full Project Title	DEFINITE-CCRI - Deal Engine, with finance, investment and technical expertise for the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative
Lead partner for deliverable	ICLEI EUROPE
Due date of deliverable	30.04.2024
Actual submission date	30.04.2024
Version	3 (1 August 2024)
Dissemination level	Public (PU)
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WP/Task related to the deliverable	WP2/Task 2.4
Document ID	DEFINITE-CCRI_D2.5_Shortlist of projects receiving PDA Support_FinalVersion_01.08.2024
Document type	Report

Executive Summary

The Shortlist of projects receiving PDA Support is the last deliverable of Work Package 2, within the umbrella of the DEFINITE-CCRI project. This document summarises in a list the projects that have been initially selected for being onboarded in the DEFINITE-CCRI pipeline to receive Technical and impact potential Assessment (TIP) and Finance and investment baseline (FIB) of the Deal Engine.

The key objectives of the deliverable are:

- **Objective 1:** Provide the general public and interested stakeholders with an overview of the projects that make part of the initial cohort of DEFINITE-CCRI.
- **Objective 2:** List the key characteristics and initial endowments of the projects selected in a standardised way.

The deliverable was submitted in September 2023, encompassing the seven projects receiving PDA, and selected based on applications received by the end of June 2023. The deliverable has been updated to incorporate the additional three selected projects, following the extension of the submission deadline until February 2024.

DEFINITE Consortium Partners

Logo	Organisation	Type	Country
	ICLEI EURO	Small and medium-sized enterprise	Germany
	Circle Economy	Non-governmental organisation	The Netherlands
	Stad Gent	Municipality	Belgium
	Bankers without Boundaries (BwB)	Non-governmental organisation	Ireland
	National Technical University of Athens (NTUA)	University	Greece

Table of Contents

<i>Executive Summary</i>	3
<i>DEFINITE Consortium Partners</i>	4
<i>Table of Contents</i>	5
<i>List of figures</i>	6
<i>List of abbreviations used</i>	6
<i>The DEFINITE-CCRI Project in a Nutshell</i>	7
<i>DEFINITE-CCRI Objectives</i>	7
<i>Factsheets on DEFINITE-CCRI projects onboarded for PDA Support</i>	11
Circular Economy Incubator Hub.....	11
Plastic Unchained.....	12
Channelling Material Flows.....	13
Circular Library Network.....	15
3D Printing Pilot Structure of geopolymers for Kutila Canal	16
FixFirst	17
Innovative membrane bioreactor for water recovery in the food industry	18
Tissel	20
Rewrap.....	21

List of figures

Figure 1 DEFINITE-CCRI PDA Support Service Timeline	8
Figure 2 Insights on DEFINITE-CCRI Onboarded projects (I)	10
Figure 3 Insights on DEFINITE-CCRI Onboarded projects (II)	10

List of abbreviations used

- AnMBR Anaerobic membrane bioreactor
- CCRI Circular Cities and Regions Initiative
- CSA Coordination and Support Action
- DNSH Do not Significant Harm Principle
- EU European Union
- FIB Financial and Investment Baseline
- PDA Project Development Assistance
- PPPs Public Private Partnerships
- TIP Technical Impact Potential
- TRL Technology Readiness Level

The DEFINITE-CCRI Project in a Nutshell

Effective investment and financing opportunities for circular economy projects in Europe are still few. For securing financing, circular economy projects must meet investors' requirements for bankability and display risk-return profiles to increase investors' trust in impactful projects aimed at advancing the transition to a more circular economy in cities and regions. In order to become less risky and more appealing for investments, projects need to be developed around new and re-designed finance solutions and business models. Transaction costs need to be decreased and the private finance community needs to be engaged to address legal, administrative and market related challenges. In response to this, the DEFINITE-CCRI project establishes a Deal Engine Mechanism, providing technical, financial and circular economy expertise through local Project Development Assistance (PDA) in an unprecedented and streamlined process to city and regional governments and to project developers. It aims to co-create and prove an end-to-end PDA process, aggregating risk mitigation, EU Taxonomy compliance, circularity criteria and technical and financial engineering in a single project development service for the CCRI's service portfolio. This will inject the financial, technical and managerial know-how into urban circular transitions and ultimately contribute to lower virgin non-renewable material use, lower GHG emissions and more just and inclusive circular employment in line with the European Green Deal, the Circular Economy Action Plan and the Bio-economy Strategy.

DEFINITE-CCRI (*Deal Engine, with finance, investment and technical expertise for the European Commission's Circular Cities and Regions Initiative – CCRI*) is a Horizon Europe funded project that has started in November 2022.

DEFINITE-CCRI Objectives

The four key objectives at the foundation of the project's vision and work plan are:

- **Objective 1:** To build and operate a deal engine for the CCRI and establish it as a sustainable service offering for cities in Europe.
- **Objective 2:** To close the gap between circular economy projects in cities and regions and investors and finance partners, and to mitigate investment risks for circular economy projects.
- **Objective 3:** To increase the investment viability of innovative, high-impact circularity projects by mitigating risk and increasing their investment readiness.
- **Objective 4:** To successfully launch four investments in circular economy projects up to 20 million Euro investment volume per project in CCRI cities and regions.

Introduction

The purpose of this document is to provide an overview of the projects shortlisted for PDA support in the period September 2023 – April 2025. The deliverable builds upon the process set out in [D 2.1 - Summary of DEFINITE-CCRI project pipeline onboarding package](#) – and carried on as part of Task 2.

Project Outlines received by the deadline of 31st June 2023 were screened for eligibility by the project consortium based on their completeness, technical excellence, quality of team composition and roadmap, replication/upscaling potential, innovation potential, baseline technical and financial information as well as circularity impact and impact on co-benefits such as GHG reduction.

Figure 1 below outlines the stages of the roll out of the DEFINITE-CCRI Deal Engine Mechanism. With the selection of the first cohort of beneficiaries, the project entered in the TIP and FIB assessment phases; related methodologies are outlined in D3.1 (Report on methodology for the Financial Impact Baseline and financial due diligence) and D4.1 (Report on methodology for the Technical and Impact Potential and technical due diligence) respectively.

Figure 1 DEFINITE-CCRI PDA Support Service Timeline

The current report provides a schematic overview of the projects in the pipeline, outlining the main characteristics of each one following a common template in the form of a factsheet. The projects will be given support by the DEFINITE-CCRI expert team for the TIP and FIB phases. By M17, the projects

suited and willing to proceed to the contracting phase will be selected and further supported until April 2025 with the subsequent steps of the Deal Engine Mechanism.

Seven projects have been onboarded to receive Project Development Assistance based on their application submitted until June 2023. However, considering that additional capacity remained available for partners to provide TIP and FIB assessments, the submission deadline was extended until February 2024. The reasons behind the deadline extension were to complete on-going conversations with project owners and give them a chance to still get their applications in, rather than attracting new projects. Therefore, the deadline extension was not promoted publicly, but was communicated to groups already attached to the project. Following this period, three additional projects were onboarded.

Project owners will receive dedicated support in relation to the financial and technical strength of their proposals. They will their TIP and FIB assessment by the end of April, and most suitable ones will be selected to proceed with the respective due diligence phases, as of May 2024:

- FIB and Financial Due Diligence: the FIB allows the collection of data, exchanges, and establishment of contact between the project teams and the DEFINITE-CCRI consortium. The FIB is divided into 7 steps, after which DEFINITE-CCRI will move more mature projects to Due Diligence Review and Project Appraisal support.
- TIP and Technical Due Diligence: TIP focuses on the technical and Impact potential assessment of projects in the pipeline. The TIP methodology and assessment criteria are developed based on a flexible methodology used to enable projects to advance the EU Green Deal in line with the EU Taxonomy, the EU Circular Economy Action Plan, and the European bioeconomy strategy. Technical due diligence support package and the process of project appraisal will help in defining what, when and how the respective technical and impact project development assistance (PDA) and support will be carried out.

Summary and interim analysis of projects onboarded into DEFINITE-CCRI

As a result of the DEFINITE-CCRI call for projects, 9 projects have been selected to move to the TIP/FIB assessment phase:

- The Circular Economy Incubator Hub of Tehdassaari, Finland
- The Plastics Unchained project, Belgium
- The Channelling Material Flow project, Belgium
- The Circular Library Network project, Iceland
- The 3D Printing Pilot Structure of geopolymer for the Kutila Canal project, Finland
- The FixFirst project, Germany
- The Innovative membrane bioreactor for water recovery in the food industry project, Austria
- The Rewrap project, Belgium
- The Tissel project, France

The nine projects represent a cumulative expected investment amount of €68.5 Million. Current stage of development is consistent across the batch, with most projects currently in the pre-feasibility and feasibility stage; only two projects are already at implementation stage and will require more targeted PDA support.

DEFINITE-CCRI Summary of Onboarded Projects

Figure 2 Insights on DEFINITE-CCRI Onboarded projects (I)

Project owners have signalled Technology readiness levels (TRL) for their projects ranging between 2 and 9, with TRL 6 and 9 – technology validate in lab research or local environment – mostly present across the portfolio.

Projects are aligned with the UN Sustainable Development Goals – in particular goals 6 to 15. In addition, all projects have declared to be aligned with EU Taxonomy principles; further alignment will be explored during the TIP phase inside DEFINITE-CCRI.

Lastly, 10 R strategies are covered by the projects, with each project focusing on 2.9 strategies simultaneously.

Figures 2 – above – and Figure 3 – below – summarise the initial information collected by the DEFINITE-CCRI project outlines.

DEFINITE-CCRI Summary of Onboarded Projects

Figure 3 Insights on DEFINITE-CCRI Onboarded projects (II)

Factsheets on DEFINITE-CCRI projects onboarded for PDA Support

Circular Economy Incubator Hub

Location: Nokia, Finland

Project owner: Cireco Finland Oy, Souranderintie 2b, Tehdassaari, 37100 Nokia

Description of the project

The Circular Economy Incubator Hub is a brownfield regeneration project. It aims to transform a former industrial area of the Island of Tehdassaari into a circular incubation space dedicated to foster research, development, and innovation across various industries and provide a space for companies to cooperate and test their CE solutions. The project aims to use an app to help create and run the circular hub.

Main resources (technological, material, time, etc.) and project context.

- **Material:** The building that will host the circular economy hub has been purchased by the project owner, but this still needs structural changes to be adapted to the hub. A conceptual idea and timeframe have been developed by project partners and needs further refinement towards CE, e.g., by developing an application that will support the development of the circular business hub.
- **Context:** the project aims to leverage on investments and PPPs as essential frameworks for distributing the costs and benefits of circular economy actions. The project requires investment pitch training and matchmaking with investors. The public administration's role should be enhanced to instil greater confidence regarding the project's potential for success.

Type of R-strategy

- Rethink
- Repair
- Reuse

Technology readiness Level TRL

2

Stakeholders involved

- Local government
- Industry and businesses
- Academia
- Local Community

Type of territory

- urban

Key sectors involved

- Construction
- Information and communication
- Industrial symbiosis?

Financial effort

- **Sought financing amount:** 36 M€
- **Type of finance sought:** grants, private investments, national and European funding
- **Current stage of project development:** pre-feasibility

Alignment with the EU Taxonomy

- ✓ Contribution to the transition to CE.
- ✓ Alignment with other EU Taxonomy objectives.
- ✓ Compliance with "DNSH"
- ✓ Compliance with minimum safeguards criteria

Potential Circular Impact and co-benefits <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct: Energy production; GHG emissions reduction • Indirect: improved waste management and efficiency; waste reduction • Gender and minority groups: job creation, economic growth and social inclusivity 	SDGs addressed 8 – Decent Work and Economic Growth 9 – Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure 10 – Sustainable Cities and Communities
Expected timeline The project owner is investigating into developing the Tehdassaari industrial site in different steps throughout the years. DEFINITE-CCRI support will be instrumental for the Design and investment planning phase as well as the development of a solid Business Plan. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design: 2021- 2026 • Inception: 2027-2033 • Implementation: 2033-2038 	Metrics and targets To be defined under the DEFINITE-CCRI pipeline

Plastic Unchained

Location: Leuven, Belgium

Project owner: Wercircle, Rue Mégarnie 2 4480 Engis

Description of the project

In the Plastics Unchained urban circular hub, several stakeholders of the city of Leuven are aiming to set up a specialised operation process to handle plastics sub stream waste. The process will produce outputs ready for high valorisation according to the specific subtypes.

By transforming smaller scale manually operated pilots into a scalable industrial blueprint, Plastic Unchained works on the intersection between materials science, mechanical engineering, digitalisation logistics and labour skills development.

Main resources (technological, material, time, etc.) and project context.

- **Material:** the project owner aims at developing a waste sorting facility using cutting edge technology to handle sub stream plastic waste. Machineries and production lines will be needed to operationalise the logistics hub (conveyor belts; scanning devices and infrastructures for homogenisation, decontamination, disinfection, compacting, preparing for transport)
- **Context:** Plastic Unchained targets plastic waste which is not captured by current waste sorting methods; the project targets in particular waste from hospitals and pharmaceutical industry. This project is also part of Leuven's Climate City Contract portfolio of Breakthrough Projects and will be included in the CCC Investment Plan.

Type of R-strategy

- Recycle
- Reuse
- Refuse

Technology readiness Level TRL

6

Stakeholders involved

- Local Government
- Academia
- Local Community

Type of territory

- Predominantly urban

Key sectors involved

- Hospital industry
- Waste

Financial effort <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sought financing amount: 3.8 M€ • Type of finance sought: loans / investments / funding / grants • Current stage of project development: pre-feasibility 	Alignment with EU Taxonomy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Contribution to the transition to CE. ✓ Alignment with other EU Taxonomy objectives. ✓ Compliance with “DNSH” ✓ Compliance with minimum safeguards criteria
Potential Circular Impact and co-benefits <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct: reduction of used material flows lost in value chain for reuse, GHG emissions reduction • Indirect: job creation; • Gender and minority groups: increased access to the labour market of people with difficulties 	SDGs addressed <p>8 – Decent Work and Economic Growth</p> <p>13 – Climate Action</p> <p>14 – Life below Water</p> <p>15 – Life on Land</p>
Expected timeline <p>With the support of DEFINITE-CCRI, the project owner is aiming at developing the business model and investment concept to present to potential investors, to start with implementation by the end of 2025.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design: 2023-2024 • Inception: 2025 • Implementation: 2026 onward 	Metrics and Targets of expected outcomes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Burned plastics avoidance • Virgin plastics replacement by recycled plastics

Channelling Material Flows

Location: Leuven, Belgium

Project owner: Leuven municipality, “Leuven2030”

Description of the project

In ‘Channelling material flows’, the project owner aims at developing a logistics system to tap into material output streams at source. The set up of satellite material banks and other logistical solutions (incl. collection rounds) will be investigated to increase the circularity potential of physical flows for high R-grade strategies.

Main resources (technological, material, time, etc.) and project context.

- **Resources:** with the aim to set up specialised material bank, the project owner is looking into developing the infrastructure and logistics set up for two types of waste: a coarse-grained collection system and a Fine-mazed collection system. The two

Type of R-strategy

- Recycle
- Reuse

Technology readiness Level TRL

6

Stakeholders involved

- Government
- Academia

<p>systems will allow for a differentiation of waste treatment according to the highest R strategy possible.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context: The project owner aims at developing a subsystem for more efficient urban mining in the context of a city-wide material bank. Material flows (building materials, textiles, electric & electronic appliances, wood, etc.) are collected in the fine-mazed collection system and feed into the Urban Circular Hub where waste streams are prepared and offered for reuse B2C and B2B. This project is also part of Leuven’s Climate City Contract portfolio of Breakthrough Projects and will be included in the CCC Investment Plan. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private industries and businesses • Community <p>Type of territory</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Predominantly urban <p>Key sectors involved</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Waste Industry • Logistics
<p>Financial effort</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sought financing amount: 3.9 M€ • Type of finance sought: loans / investments / funding / grants • Current stage of project development: pre-feasibility 	<p>Alignment with EU Taxonomy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Contribution to the transition to CE. ✓ Alignment with other EU Taxonomy objectives. ✓ Compliance with “DNSH” ✓ Compliance with minimum safeguards criteria
<p>Potential Circular Impact and co-benefits</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct: reduction of used material flows lost in value chain for reuse • Indirect: job creation, increased share of renewable and secondary raw materials in overall material demand; Increased self-sufficiency / self-reliance; Reduced waste generation; Reduced incineration and landfilling activities • Gender and minority groups: increased access to the labour market of people with difficulties 	<p>SDGs addressed</p> <p>8 – Decent Work and Economic Growth</p> <p>9 – Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure</p> <p>11 – Sustainable Cities and Communities</p> <p>13 – Climate Action</p>
<p>Expected timeline:</p> <p>With the support of DEFINITE-CCRI, the project owner is aiming at developing the business model and investment concept to present to potential investors, to start with implementation by the end of 2025.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design: 2023-2024 • Inception: 2025 • Implementation: 2026 onward 	<p>Metrics and Targets of expected outcomes</p> <p>To be defined under the DEFINITE-CCRI pipeline</p>

Circular Library Network

Location: Reykjavik, Iceland

Project owner: The Circular Library Network previously Munasafn RVK Tool Library, Reykjavik, Capital Region

Description of the project

The project aims to develop a decentralised borrowing system allowing libraries to integrate the Circular Library Network and empower communities to share resources throughout Europe. The project's main objective is to establish peer-to-peer support and system through a library of things organisation in the EU to reduce waste, enhance circularity, and eliminate the need for individual ownership. Via the Circular Library Network, communities across Europe are encouraged to set up their own sharing stations, fostering a culture of sharing and community bonding.

Main resources (technological, material, time, etc.) and project contextual conditions.

- Resources:** The project's business model combines a Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) platform and sales of self-checkout system parts. The SaaS platform aims to provide a digital solution for seamless resource sharing and management, offering features like inventory management and reservation systems. The project also aims at developing parts for building self-checkout systems using existing furniture, enabling libraries and communities to set up their own sharing hubs.
- Context:** Household emissions in Iceland are heavily influenced by imported goods, contributing to 71% of emissions per household yearly. The project will raise awareness and help minimise e-waste and emissions in Iceland and the EU. Many different stakeholders have already been involved; pre-feasibility study has been completed.

Type of R-strategy

- Rethink
- Reuse
- Recycle

Technology readiness Level TRL

5

Stakeholders involved

- Local Government
- Libraries
- Community
- Businesses

Type of territory

- Urban, regional and European

Key sectors involved

- Information and Communication

Financial effort

- **Sought financing amount:** 2M EUR
- **Type of finance sought:** Grants, Loans from financial institutions, National or European funding
- **Current stage of project development:** Feasibility study

Alignment with EU Taxonomy

- ✓ Contribution to the transition to CE.
- ✓ Alignment with other EU Taxonomy objectives.
- ✓ Compliance with "DNSH"
- ✓ Compliance with minimum safeguards criteria

Potential Circular Impact and co-benefits

- **Direct:** reduced GHG emissions, reduced consumption
- **Indirect:** job opportunities and economic growth
- **Gender and minority groups:** fostered gender equality and inclusivity; increased intergenerational connection; development of entrepreneurial skills; promotion of

SDGs addressed

- 10 – Reduced Inequalities
- 12 – Responsible Consumption and Production
- 13 – Climate Action

inclusivity, accessibility, and support networks for racial minorities, LGBTQ communities.	
Expected timeline The project is currently in the design and pre-feasibility stage. According to the project owner, full implementation and commercialisation are expected to happen by 2027. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design: 2024 - 2025 • Inception: 2025-2026 • Implementation: 2026 - 2027 	Metric and target of expected outcomes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % reduction in material consumption • Increased self-sufficiency • Reduced waste generation

3D Printing Pilot Structure of geopolymers for Kutila Canal

Location: Lappeenranta, Finland

Project owner: Hyperion Robotics Oy, Keran Hallit, loading bay 305, Karamalmintie 2, 02630 Espoo, Finland & Municipality of Lappeenranta

Description of the project

The project aims to use side-stream tailings from the regional mining operations to create geopolymers concrete and 3D print. The products of the 3D printing operations will be used for the construction of armoured units for the Kutila Canal infrastructure.

Main resources (technological, material, time, etc.) and project conditions.

- **Resources:** the project is in the R&D phase. Material resources needed for the development of the projects span from the development of a material bank for mining tailings; the development of industrial facilities for 3D printing of the armoured units.
- **Context:** Lappeenranta City grapples with a significant mining tailings issue resulting from extensive regional mining activities. These tailings pose environmental challenges, including water and soil contamination. They contain hazardous substances, impacting both human health and wildlife. Innovative solutions like geopolymers concrete are explored to repurpose the tailings. The pre-feasibility study has been conducted and the main stakeholders have been involved in developing the project idea.

Type of R-strategy

- Recycle
- Repurpose
- Recover
- Reuse

Technology readiness Level TRL

5

Stakeholders involved

- Local Government
- Industry and businesses
- Academia

Type of territory

- Urban and regional

Key sectors involved

- Mining
- Construction

Financial effort

- **Sought financing amount:** 3.3M EUR

Alignment with EU Taxonomy

- ✓ Contribution to the transition to CE.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Type of finance sought: Private investments, National or European funding • Current stage of project development: Feasibility study 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Alignment with other EU Taxonomy objectives. ✓ Compliance with “DNSH” ✓ Compliance with minimum safeguards criteria
<p>Potential Circular Impact and co-benefits</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct: reduced GHG emissions, climate adaptation and resilience, reduction of used material flows lost in value chain for reuse, biodiversity restoration • Indirect: job creation • Gender and minority groups: N/A 	<p>SDGs addressed</p> <p>12 – Responsible Consumption and Production</p> <p>13 – Climate Action</p> <p>14 – Life below Water</p>
<p>Expected timeline</p> <p>The project owner aims at starting the first activities during fall 2023, with the aim of further testing the 3D printing solution. Full-scale implementation for the purpose identified is expected to take place in 2025.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design: 2023 - 2024 • Inception: 2024-2025 • Implementation: 2025 - onwards 	<p>Metrics and Targets of expected outcomes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • increase share of secondary raw materials in overall material demand • reduction of virgin material use and use of cement

FixFirst

Location: Berlin, Germany

Project owner: FixFirst, c/o Factory Berlin, Rheinsberger Str. 76/77, 10115 Berlin

Description of the project

The project aims to develop a repair platform as a service including repair vouchers programs for electronic products repairing. The project aims to reduce electronic waste.

Main resources (technological, material, time, etc.) and project conditions.

- **Resources:** the project has a strong IT component, as such, the main infrastructural need is in relation with software development, in connection with the development of the project business model. The platform is currently being developed.
- **Context:** The FixFirst platform is meant to be used by cities to facilitate the reduction of electronic waste at an urban level. The

Type of R-strategy

- Repair
- Reduce
- Reuse

Technology readiness Level TRL

9

Stakeholders involved

- Local Government

<p>involvement of local government should allow for an easier access to local service providers.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Industry and businesses <p>Type of territory</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mainly urban <p>Key sectors involved</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information and Communication
<p>Financial effort</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sought financing amount: 700 000 EUR Type of finance sought: Private investments, grants, national or European funding Current stage of project development: Implementation phase 	<p>Alignment with EU Taxonomy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Contribution to the transition to CE. ✓ Alignment with other EU Taxonomy objectives. ✓ Compliance with “DNSH” ✓ Compliance with minimum safeguards criteria
<p>Potential Circular Impact and co-benefits</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct: reduced GHG emissions, climate adaptation and resilience, reduction of used material flows lost in value chain for reuse Indirect: biodiversity restoration; job creation Gender and minority groups: N/A 	<p>SDGs addressed</p> <p>11 – Sustainable Cities and Communities</p> <p>12 – Responsible Consumption and Production</p> <p>13 – Climate Action</p>
<p>Expected timeline</p> <p>The project is currently making its first steps in the inception phase, with full implementation foreseen by 2024.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Design: N/A Inception: 2023 -2024 Implementation: 2024 	<p>Metrics and Targets of expected outcomes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> GHG emissions avoidance

Innovative membrane bioreactor for water recovery in the food industry

Location: Sieghartskirchen, Austria

Project owner: BOKU University, Gregor-Mendel-Straße 33, 1180 Wien, Austria & Fleischwaren Berger GesmbH & Co KG, Koglerstraße 8 A-3443 Sieghartskirchen

Description of the project

The project aims to develop a large-scale plant of an anaerobic membrane bioreactor (AnMBR) using wastewater from the meat processing industry to produce renewable energy (biogas), process wastewater and produce high valuable fertilizer from organic waste.

<p>The project contributes to the transition to circular economy, offering a solution that transforms organic waste into ecological fertilizers for the agricultural sector, and biogas that ensure the industry energy self-sufficiency. It also improves the processing of wastewater allowing industries to become water self-sufficient.</p>	
<p>Main resources (technological, material, time, etc.) and project conditions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resources: the project owner aims to go from a pilot plant into a large-scale plant. As such, the project needs cutting-edge industrial facilities able to host the AnMBR processing. • Context: The large-scale pilot plant will be implemented following the experiment run through the Symsites pilot plant funded within the Horizon Europe project and running from 2023 until 2026. SYMSITES aims at developing new technologies and solutions based on the Industrial and Urban symbiosis (I-US) concept, for local and regional collaborations among diverse actors (Citizens, Municipalities and Enterprises) and sectors improving the sustainability of the use of industrial and societal resources starting from wastewater and waste materials. 	<p>Type of R-strategy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recover
	<p>Technology readiness Level TRL</p> <p>4</p>
	<p>Stakeholders involved</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local Government • Industry and businesses • Academia
	<p>Type of territory</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • urban • Peri-urban
	<p>Key sectors involved</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agriculture • Water supply, Sewerage • Waste management and remediation activities
<p>Financial effort</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sought financing amount: 7.2 M EUR • Type of finance sought: Loans from commercial banks, private investments • Current stage of project development: Feasibility study 	<p>Alignment with EU Taxonomy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Contribution to the transition to CE. ✓ Alignment with other EU Taxonomy objectives. ✓ Compliance with “DNSH” ✓ Compliance with minimum safeguards criteria
<p>Potential Circular Impact and co-benefits</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct: reduced GHG emissions, climate adaptation and resilience, reduction of used material flows lost in value chain for reuse • Indirect: improved waste management and efficiency, Reduced harmful ecological footprint • Gender and minority groups: job creation, gender inclusivity 	<p>SDGs addressed</p> <p>6 – Clean Water and Sanitation</p> <p>7 – Affordable and Clean Energy</p> <p>9 – Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure</p>
<p>Expected timeline</p>	<p>Metrics and Targets</p>

The project is currently in the design phase and feasibility study for an industrial upscale of the pilot being development under Symsites. Full implementation is expected to take place starting from 2028.

- **Design:** 2023 - 2026
- **Inception:** 2026 -2028
- **Implementation:** 2028 – 2029

- Increased share of renewable energy in energy demand
- Increase self-sufficiency/ self-reliance
- Reduced waste generation

Tissel

Location: Roubaix, France

Project owner: Municipality of Roubaix

Description of the project

Tissel is a circular business hub project for SMEs, based in an old factory that was about to be abandoned by its previous owner. The City of Roubaix bought the factory with the purpose to refurbish and renovate it and dedicate the space to develop a pool of circular economy related SMEs. The project aims to fully refurbish the old building in a frugal, low-tech and circular way under the current safety and accessibility standards and dedicate the space to CE businesses.

Main resources (technological, material, time, etc.) and project conditions.

- **Resources:** City of Roubaix owns an old building (the Tissel factory) leasing part of the space to seven companies on site. The city aims to renovate the building and transforming it into an energy efficient one.
- **Context:** Renovations to the building imply restoration activities, renovation of the rooftop, insulation of the building envelope and windows sub substitution, while using low-carbon energy supply (urban heating network, installation of PV panels). Once renovations will be completed, the space will be hosting additional circular economy SMEs, space will be dedicated to provide business incubation opportunities, and organize different types of events.

Type of R-strategy

- Reuse
- Repurpose
- Repair and maintenance
- Remanufacture
- Refurbish

Technology readiness Level TRL

6

Stakeholders involved

- Local and national Governments
- Industry and businesses

Type of territory

- urban

Key sectors involved

- Waste
- Energy
- Industrial Symbiosis
- Information and Communication

Financial effort

- Sought financing amount: 12.2 M EUR

Alignment with EU Taxonomy

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Type of finance sought: Grants, loans from commercial banks, loans from financial institutions, private investments, national and European funding • Current stage of project development: Feasibility study 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Contribution to the transition to CE ✓ Alignment with other EU Taxonomy objectives. ✓ Compliance with “DNSH” ✓ Compliance with minimum safeguards criteria.
<p>Potential Circular Impact and co-benefits</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct: reduced GHG emissions, climate adaptation and resilience, reduction of used material flows lost in value chain for reuse • Indirect: improved waste management and efficiency, reduced GHG emissions • Gender and minority groups: social integration and job creation for vulnerable groups 	<p>SDGs addressed</p> <p>7 – Affordable and Clean Energy</p> <p>8 – Decent Work and Economic Growth</p> <p>9 – Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure</p> <p>11 – Sustainable Cities and Communities</p> <p>12 – Responsible Consumption and Production</p>
<p>Expected timeline</p> <p>The project is currently in the design phase and feasibility study. Full implementation is expected to take place starting from 2028.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design: 2022-2024 • Inception: 2023- 2024 • Implementation: from 2024 	<p>Metrics and Targets</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce material consumption • Increase share of renewable energy in energy demand • Increase self-sufficiency/ self-reliance • Reduce waste generation • Reduce incineration and landfilling activities

Rewrap

Location: Ghent, Belgium

Description of the project

<p>The project aims to bring to the market a reusable pallet wrap made from single-use big plastic bags meant to replace plastic wraps. The project aims to create new job opportunities for social ateliers.</p>	
<p>Main resources (technological, material, time, etc.) and project conditions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resources: the project owner aims to develop a solution that substitute single-use pallet wrap foil. The solution 'eats' two types of single-use material streams and creates an automated loop logistics system for a wrapping product that facilitates the reuse of different parts of loads, such as the pallets. • Context: Rewrap will develop an innovative pallet wrap made of large bags and aimed at replacing single-use plastic wrap. So far, the product has been tested with regard to its strength capacity, however, other types of wraps are also planned to be produced to cover a wider range of loads and to be used in a variety of sectors related to the transportation of loads. The proposed solution is highly innovative and aligned to the EU Green Deal. 	<p>Type of R-strategy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reuse • Repair • Refuse <p>Technology readiness Level TRL 7</p> <p>Stakeholders involved</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local Government • Industry and businesses <p>Type of territory</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • urban • <p>Key sectors involved</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Waste
<p>Financial effort</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sought financing amount: Not specified at this stage • Type of finance sought: Loans or equity • Current stage of project development: Very early stage but the proposed BM is a traditional sale model with potential opps for cleaning and repair services – they're unconvinced of the demand for PaaS offering 	<p>Alignment with EU Taxonomy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Contribution to the transition to CE. ✓ Alignment with other EU Taxonomy objectives.
<p>Potential Circular Impact and co-benefits</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct: reduction of material consumption, reduction of waste • Indirect: GHG emissions reduction, improved waste management and efficiency • Gender and minority groups: job creation for vulnerable groups 	<p>SDGs addressed</p> <p>8 – Decent Work and Economic Growth</p> <p>9 – Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure</p> <p>11 – Sustainable Cities and Communities</p> <p>12 – Responsible Consumption and Production</p> <p>13 – Climate Action</p> <p>17 – Partnerships for the Goals</p>
<p>Expected timeline To be defined alongside project leaders as this starts N/A</p>	<p>Metrics and Targets</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased share of renewable

	<p>energy in energy demand</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Increase self-sufficiency/ self-reliance• Reduced waste generation
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